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Improvement in Foamability/stability Test Rigs for CO₂ Foam EOR Screening Evaluation

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SUMMARY

To screen effective foaming agents for CO₂ Foam EOR, foamability/stability test is performed as visual evaluation and/or slimtube apparatus under high pressure and high temperature (HPHT) condition in reservoir. There are several ways for generating foams: i.e. bubbling, stirring, and mixing through porous media (ex. sandpack, glassbeads, etc.). The bubbling method is usually applicable in the open system at ambient pressure condition. The mixing through porous media is applicable in HPHT condition, but mainly used in flooding tests in which mixing efficiency might be minimal because of just one time chance for injectants (CO₂ and foaming agent) to create foam. The stirring can be applied into closed/pressurized system such as PVT apparatus that provides visual observation through glass cell/window. In this paper, stirring and mixing-through-porous-media were used in the foamability test rig and the slimtube apparatus, respectively.

The existing rigs in our laboratory were modified for evaluating CO₂ foam. In general, magnetic stirring system is equipped in PVT apparatus to equilibrate fluid samples, however; the iron magnets could not be resistant to our experimental condition. Then, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-encapsulated magnetic stirrer was used as alternative material. The PTFE stirrer was wheel shape with 4 blades on both surfaces of upper and lower for more stirring power. From material aspects, PTFE is universal chemical/corrosion resistance under existence of oil and hydrocarbon gas mixture, however; our experimental environment (mixing of CO₂ + formation water) rapidly becomes severer as pressure/temperature increase. The stirrer was expanded and chipped due to CO₂ corrosion, and stuck in cylinder-shape metal device location at the bottom of glass cell, although it was originally set with small clearance to rotate freely. This expansion resulted insufficient stirring power to create foams. In the slimtube flooding test to evaluate apparent viscosity increase by CO₂ foam, a visual cell was equipped at the downstream location of the sandpack to check ideal foam creation. However, our first trial was failed and required modification.

This paper demonstrates how we improved the foam creation sufficiently under the reservoir condition for appropriate evaluation.

Introduction

CO₂ EOR has been commercially used to produce more oil for more than 40 years, and considered as one of the promising EOR application. Among possible types of gas EOR, CO₂ gas injection is currently most favored not only for enhancing oil production but also for storing CO₂ in oil producing reservoirs. According to outcomes of the United Nation’s Climate Change Conference in Paris held in November 30th-December 12th, 2015, the Paris agreement decided to limit global temperature increase below 2 degrees Celsius⁽¹⁾. For achieving this goal, it is highly motivated for industry to pursue a Carbon Capture Storage (CCS) technology that can comply with the strict environmental requirements. From this point of view, the CO₂-injection in oil producing reservoir has both aspects of EOR and CCS. According to the National Energy Technology Laboratory (NETL) survey⁽²⁾ in 2011, CO₂ EOR provides approximately 280,000 bbls/d oil production. This amount was over 5 percent of the total U.S. crude oil production. The reasons why CO₂ EOR had expanded in the U.S. were considered to be due to sustainable natural CO₂ source availability as well as existence of CO₂ pipeline network, and this infrastructure is expected to allow access to large anthropogenic CO₂ sources through advances of the CCS technology. In upcoming years by 2020, the CO₂ EOR project and production were predicted to keep expanding as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 CO₂-EOR Operations and CO₂ sources in 2014 and 2020 (projected).⁽³⁾

Accordingly in E&P industry, optimization of CO₂ EOR is becoming more important by overcoming typical disadvantages of the conventional CO₂ flooding. There are several typical problems of CO₂ flooding such as fingering caused by instability in the CO₂ displacement process, gas segregation, gas override, and CO₂ channeling through high permeable streak/fracture. Such CO₂-bypass is resulting poor volumetric sweep and deterioration of oil recovery. These problems such as CO₂ channeling can be avoided and/or mitigated by effective mobility control. For reducing the CO₂ mobility, two countermeasures are attracting attention. One is to increase its viscosity, and another is to decrease the high/fractured permeability. To realize the former approach, a focus is set on increasing the CO₂ viscosity to lower its mobility. Thus, it becomes possible to achieve a more favorable mobility ratio for enhancing the oil recovery. To optimize the mobility control, many types of CO₂-foaming agents have been developed for applying CO₂ foam flooding instead of injecting CO₂ alone. CO₂-foam can reduce the gas mobility in fractures or high permeable streak. Consequently, this

can divert CO₂-flow into previously by-passed layers in oil-saturated zone. In terms of optimizing CO₂ foam flooding, a crucial point is its foamability and static stability. To evaluate these fundamental characteristics of CO₂ foaming agents, foamability/static stability tests are performed in general. When performing these tests, there are 4 types of methodologies for mixing CO₂ and foaming agent for foam generation. This paper focuses on magnetic stirring method for evaluating foamability at high pressure and high temperature (HPHT) condition: typically around 2,000-5,000 psi, 80 °C and higher.

Figure 2 Schematic vertical and areal sweep image of CO₂ flooding and CO₂ foam flooding. CO₂ flooding causes channeling through high permeable layers, and gravity segregation occurs in each layer. This leads to unexpected early gas breakthrough and more bypassed oil. Foam flooding can create more homogeneous gas front by better mobility control. This can decrease bypassed oil and improve oil recovery.

Method for Foam Generation

From a recent citation, many references that explain about foam generation methods and conditions were found. The literature survey results are summarized in Table 1. The list includes not only CO₂ foam research but also N₂/air foam because these also contain information on foam generation.

Table 1 Citation results of foamability/stability tests applying various foam generation methods.

Source	Injectant (gas)	Foamability/Static/Core Flooding Test				Experimental Purpose
		Temperature	Pressure	Foam Generation Method	Apparatus	
Bai et al. (2005) ⁽⁴⁾	CO ₂	25°C	1500psig	bubbling	sapphire visual cell, needle at bottom	for foam stability test
Yu et al. (2012) ⁽⁵⁾	CO ₂	25°C	1500psi	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	glass bead packed column (GBPC)	for foamability test
Belhajj et al. (2014) ⁽⁶⁾	CO ₂	room temp.	atm. press.	bubbling	glass column with syringe	for foam stability test
		NA	1000psi of conf. press.	co-injecting w/gas	CFS-200	for core flooding
Singh et al. (2014) ⁽⁷⁾	N ₂	room temp.	atm. press.	shaking vigorously	glass test tube	for preliminary static foam test
		room temp.	atm. press.	bubbling	graduated glass cylinder, needle at bottom	for foamability/static foam test
		55, 75, 95°C	atm. press.	bubbling	transparent cylinder, needle at bottom	for foamability/static foam test
		room temp.	1500psi of conf. press.	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	sandpack	for foam flow experiment
Singh et al. (2015) ⁽⁸⁾	CO ₂	room temp.	atm. press.	shaking vigorously	foamability test tube	for foamability test
		room temp.	1300psi	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	sandpack (40-70 mesh Ottawa sand)	for foam texture analysis
		room temp.	1500psi of conf. press.	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	sandpack (40-70 mesh Ottawa sand)	for foam flow experiment
Singh et al. (2016) ⁽⁹⁾	N ₂	same as SPE169126				
Li et al. (2016) ⁽¹⁰⁾	Air	25°C	atm. press.	bubbling	gas distributor at bottom	for foam fractionation
Hernando et al. (2016) ⁽¹¹⁾	N ₂	NA	NA	Ross-Miles Method ⁽¹⁴⁾ (turbulent mixing by drop to solution)	77cm height graduated cylinder	for foamability/stability test
		20°C	NA	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	sandpack (φ37-38%)	for core flooding
San et al. (2016) ⁽¹²⁾	CO ₂	25°C	1500psi	co-injecting in porous media w/gas	sandstone core	for foamability/stability test
Zhu et al. (2016) ⁽¹³⁾	N ₂	NA	atm. press.	stirring	Waring Blender (3000r/min)	for static bulk foam test
		80.4°C	18.38MPa	co-injecting w/gas	CFS-700 HPHT chemical flooding system	for core flooding

Remarks: atm. press. = atmospheric pressure
conf. press. = confining pressure
NA = not available

As shown above, there are several ways for generating foams: i.e. vigorous shaking, bubbling, stirring, co-injecting with gas through porous media (ex. sandpack, glass beads packed column, etc.) and turbulent dropping foaming agent solution from certain height to the same solution in glass cylinder. Hand shaking is the simplest method, and applied to preliminary screening test at ambient condition. The bubbling method is usually applicable in the open system at ambient pressure condition, however in some cases, the bubbling method is carried out at mildly pressurized condition. The co-injection with gas through porous media is applicable in HPHT condition, but mainly used in flooding tests in which mixing efficiency might be minimal because of having only single opportunity for injectants (CO₂ and foaming agent) to generate foam. Based on US-patent/literature survey, typical testing rig set-up images are summarized in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Typical foam generating methods from citation: propeller stirring, bubbling, magnetic stirring, dropping, and co-injecting with gas in porous media.

The stirring method could be applied into both of closed/pressurized systems such as PVT apparatus that provides visual observation through glass cell/window. In this paper, stirring and mixing-through-porous-media methods were used in the foamability test rig and the slimtube apparatus, respectively. The existing testing rigs in our laboratory were used and modified for evaluating CO₂ foam.

Stirring by Iron Magnet

In general, stirring system is equipped in PVT apparatus to achieve equilibrium of fluid samples. Figure 4 shows the Phase Behavior System installed in our laboratory for conventional PVT analysis. PVT glass cell is set in air bath to control temperature, and reservoir pressure can be attained. Fluid equilibrium is achieved by stirring system that consists of impeller driven by iron magnets. Behavior of fluid in the PVT cell can be observed through glass slit. For our CO₂ foam EOR study, we took convenient and cost-saving approach by converting this existing apparatus into a foamability/stability testing rig.

Figure 4 Phase equilibrium apparatus for foaming evaluation at reservoir condition.

However, our plan did not work at first, because of material problems at HPHT condition. The problem occurred in the stirring-system in Figure 5. The stirring-system consists of 3 parts: impeller, iron magnets and polyether ether ketone (PEEK) housing. The cylinder-shaped magnets are set in the housing with the impeller. Subsequently, the assembled stirring-system is set in another housing at the bottom of PVT cell, and then rotated by outside magnet. The assembled stirring-system is in direct contact with the fluid (mixture of saline water and CO₂) at HPHT condition during experiment. This condition is severely corrosive to the materials used. The PEEK housing and iron magnets became visibly expanded due to corrosion. The latter, in particular, showed severe corrosion-induced expansion in short time as shown in right photograph of Figure 5. This resulted in loss of clearance between the stirring-system and the housing of PVT cell, and it was not able to rotate due to jamming.

Figure 5 Photograph of stirring system consisting of impeller, iron magnets and PEEK housing. The iron magnets severely inflated after use of foaming test at reservoir condition. The corrosion-induced expansion caused crunch resulting malfunction of rotating.

Stirring by PTFE Magnet

For overcoming this problem, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-encapsulated magnetic stirrer was used to replace the original stirring-system. PTFE is widely applied in many industries⁽¹⁸⁾ in preference to other materials because of its better characteristics such as chemical resistance, heat resistance, friction coefficient, dielectric strength, toughness, or weather resistance. Its characteristics can satisfy more complex requirements needing combination of such properties. In the CO₂ foam EOR, experimental condition might be sour-corrosive environment that particularly requires chemical resistance materials in testing rig. It was expected that this new material could improve the performance and extend life of the stirrer. The new stirrer was wheel shape with 4 blades on both surfaces of upper and lower for more stirring power.

PTFE is known to have universal chemical/corrosion resistant characteristics under existence of oil and hydrocarbon gas mixture. However, for the mixing of CO₂ and formation water, the experimental environment rapidly becomes harsher as pressure/temperature increase. Its working life was better than that of the original stirring-system, however the PTFE magnet suffered the same jamming issue after all. The stirrer became expanded due to CO₂ corrosion (see Figure 6), and stuck in cylinder-shape metal device location at the bottom of glass cell, although it is originally set with small clearance to rotate freely. This expansion-induced unrotatable condition resulted insufficient stirring power to create foams.

Figure 6 Photograph of PTFE encapsulated magnet before/after use of foaming test at reservoir condition.

Stirring by Neodymium Magnet

Further approach was taken by replacing material of magnets. Namely, the neodymium magnets were replaced with the original iron ones. Adequately coated neodymium has high anti-corrosive ability. Furthermore, it has stronger magnetic power than the iron and PTFE-encapsulated magnets. In long term use, it could be corroded, but its life was sufficient for our experimental conditions. Figure 7 shows foam generated successfully by maintaining enough rotating power during experiment. Consequently, the static foamability and stability testing rig diverted from conventional PVT apparatus became a reliable. However, even the neodymium magnets system could

Figure 7 Photograph of foamability/stability test at HPHT condition. Successfully, foam was generated in PVT cell by stirring.

not be used permanently for multiple operation at HPHT conditions. It still needs to be replaced when its corrosion-induced expansion level exceeds the working limit.

Foam Evaluation by Slimtube Test Rig

Foamability/stability test is convenient and useful for preliminary screening of foaming agents, however; engineers need further information such as dynamic characteristics which represents mobility controlling capability directly. Thus, slimtube test is performed for evaluating apparent viscosity of foam. A schematic and photographs of the test rig are shown in Figures 8 and 9, respectively. Foaming agent solution and CO₂ were co-injected through the sandpack for foam generation. Foaming status was checked by visual inspection through sight glass equipped at the downstream location of the sandpack. In this paper, delta pressure was monitored continuously on the basis of pressure transducers set at the inlet/outlet of slimtube.

Figure 8 Schematic image of slimtube test rig for evaluating foam. Specification of slimtube : inner diameter of 4.7mm and length of 12m. For foam generation, both fluids (foaming agent solution and CO₂) are co-injected through sandpack. Foaming status can be observed through sight glass. Two pressure transducers (PT-1 and 2) are located at inlet/outlet of slimtube, and then delta pressure can be calculated using both monitoring results during experiment.

The delta pressure were recorded for each case: water injection, CO₂ injection, and CO₂ foam injection. Subsequently, all records were compared with the baseline case (i.e. water injection) by normalizing. The comparison was shown in Figure 10. The baseline case of water injection shows stable delta pressure as the standard (i.e. 1.0). The CO₂ injection case shows smaller delta pressure than that of the baseline. This is consistent with lower CO₂ viscosity versus water. In case of CO₂ foam injection, delta pressure is smoothly getting higher than that of the baseline, and reaches up to 1.3 ΔP after 1.1PV injected. However, the smooth upward trend is not maintained, and became unstable showing severe fluctuation. The general trend

Figure 9 Photographs of slimtube test rig. The main body of the system can be set in air bath to control temperature.

changes into downward trend after 1.1PV while showing instantaneous peak values intermittently. In visual inspection through the sight glass, a type of slug flow (i.e. liquid-gas two phase flow) was observed during those fluctuating ΔP . Due to some reason, the mixing in the sandpack was not able to generate consistent foam. In comparison between sole CO_2 and CO_2 foam injections, during pore volume injected of 0.6-1.0, ΔP was higher in the latter than the former. This showed the increase of apparent viscosity by foam generated. Our way forward is to re-design the sandpack specification to avoid slug flow during whole experiment, so that more proper evaluation of the mobility could be achieved.

Figure 10 Preliminary results of slimtube tests. Three cases: water injection, sole CO_2 injection and CO_2 foam injection were performed.

Conclusions

- From a recent citation, many references revealed that foamability/stability tests were performed at ambient conditions. For realistic evaluation, it was considered better to conduct such screening at the reservoir conditions. Thus, in our laboratory, the existing conventional PVT analysing rig was diverted to the foamability/stability test rig by minor modification.
- According to literature/US-patent survey, shaking, bubbling, stirring by propeller, and co-injection with gas through porous media were found as typical foam generation methods. For the purpose of foamability/stability test at HPHT conditions, stirring system is considered to be preferred. Our diverted PVT rig applied a stirring system with propeller and iron magnets. This original stirring system was found to be inadequate for the use in corrosive fluid environment at HPHT conditions.
- The neodymium magnets, whose surfaces were coated by anti-corrosion material, were introduced as a replacement to the original iron magnets in the stirring system of our diverted rig. This change allowed the rig to have both corrosion resistance and sufficient rotating power for foam generation at HPHT conditions.
- From a cost efficiency point of view considering the recent low oil price environment, the diversion of existing experimental apparatus was a worth approach compared with a large investment required for purchase of dedicated experimental apparatus.
- The slimtube test could give dynamic evaluation of foaming agents. Co-injection method using sandpack could be generally used for this purpose, however its specification must be carefully designed to assure adequate foam generation.

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References

1. Center for Climate and Energy Solutions. 2015. OUTCOMES OF THE U.N. CLIMATE CHANGE CONFERENCE IN PARIS. 21st Session of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP 21).
2. Enick, R.M., and Olsen, D.K. 2012. Mobility and Conformance Control for Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) via Thickeners, Foams, and Gels – A Detailed Literature Review of 40 Years of Research. DOE/NETL-2012/1540.
3. Kuuskraa, V. and Wallace, M. 2014. CO₂-EOR set for growth as new CO₂ supplies emerge. *OGJ Newsletter* (04/07/2014).
4. Bai, B., Grigg, R., Yi Liu, Y., and Zeng, Z.W. 2005. Adsorption Kinetics of Surfactant Used in CO₂-Foam Flooding Onto Berea Sandstone. SPE-95920-MS. presented at SPE A, 9-12 October, Dallas, Texas. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/95920-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/95920-MS)
5. Yu, J., An, C., Mo, D., Liu, N., and Lee, R.L. 2012. Foam Mobility Control for Nanoparticle-Stabilized Supercritical CO₂ Foam. SPE-153336-MS. presented at SPE Improved Oil Recovery Symposium, 14-18 April, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/153336-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/153336-MS)
6. Belhaj, A., AlQuraishi, A., and Al-Mahdy, O. 2014. Foamability and Foam Stability of Several Surfactants Solutions: The Role of Screening and Flooding. SPE-172185-MS. presented at SPE Saudi Arabia Section Technical Symposium and Exhibition, 21-24 April, Al-Khobar, Saudi Arabia. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/172185-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/172185-MS)
7. Singh, R., and Mohanty, K.K. 2014. Synergistic Stabilization of Foams by a Mixture of Nanoparticles and Surfactants. SPE-169126-MS. presented at SPE Improved Oil Recovery Symposium, 12-16 April, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/169126-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/169126-MS)
8. Singh, R., Gupta, A., Mohanty, K.K., Huh, C., Lee, D., and Cho, H. 2015. Fly Ash Nanoparticle-Stabilized CO₂-in-Water Foams for Gas Mobility Control Applications. SPE-175057-MS. presented at SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition, 28-30 September, Houston, Texas, USA. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/175057-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/175057-MS)
9. Singh, R., and Mohanty, K.K. 2016. Foams Stabilized by In-Situ Surface-Activated Nanoparticles in Bulk and Porous Media. SPE-170942-PA. *SPE Journal* 1(2):121-130. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/170942-PA](https://doi.org/10.2118/170942-PA)
10. Li, R., Wu, Z., Wangb, Y., Ding, L., and Wang, Y. 2016. Role of PH-induced structural change in protein aggregation in foam fractionation of bovine serum albumin. *Biotechnology Reports* (9):46-52. [dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2016.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2016.01.002)
11. Hernando, L., Bertin, H.J., Omari, A., Dupuis, G., and Zaitoun, A. 2016. Polymer-Enhanced Foams for Water Profile Control. SPE-179581-MS. presented at SPE Improved Oil Recovery Conference, 11-13 April, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/179581-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/179581-MS)
12. San, J., Wang, S., Yu, J., Lee, R., and Liu, N. 2016. Nanoparticle Stabilized CO₂ Foam: Effect of Different Ions. SPE-179628-MS. presented at SPE Improved Oil Recovery Conference, 11-13 April, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/179628-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/179628-MS)
13. Zhu, Y., Xu, Q., and Luo, Y. 2016. Studies on Foam Flooding Formulation for Complex Fault Block Sandstone Reservoir. SPE-182857-MS. presented at Abu Dhabi International Petroleum Exhibition & Conference, 7-10 November, Abu Dhabi, UAE. [dx.doi.org/10.2118/182857-MS](https://doi.org/10.2118/182857-MS)
14. Ross, J., and Miles, G.D. 1941. An Apparatus for Comparison of Foaming Properties of Soaps and Detergents. *Oil & Soap*, May 1941, P. 99-102. [dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02545418](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02545418)
15. Reed, T.D., Pickell, M.B., and Volk, L.J. 2004. Foam generator and viscometer apparatus and process. US Patent No. 6,807,849 B1.
16. Collazo, S.G., Guaynabo, and Rico, P. 1996. Foam fractionator. US Patent No. 5,562,821 A.
17. Bender, C.E. 1979. Magnetic stirrer apparatus. US Patent No. 4,162,855.
18. Baldassarre, L., and Pelella, M. 2012. 'C' Type PTFE Gaskets Performances in High Pressure Sour Applications. Proceedings of the Forty-First Turbomachinery Symposium. September 24-27. Houston, Texas